

Human-Systems Integration for Driving Automation Systems: Holistic Approach for Driver Role Integration and Automation Allocation for European Mobility Needs

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Abstract. The EU H2020 funded project HADRIAN addresses specific challenges of human-systems integration (HSI) to bring together real drivers with complex and smart technologies to form safe, acceptable, and meaningful system outcomes. The HADRIAN (Holistic Approach for Driver Role Integration and Automation Allocation for European Mobility Needs) project investigates the definition of safe and acceptable driver roles for higher levels of automated driving with 16 research and industrial partners. This paper briefly reviews the field of HSI and postulates two dominant challenges for HSI in the domain of automated driving that will be addressed as part of HADRIAN: first, the impact of restricting the search in traditional solution spaces along prevalent organizational boundaries. Secondly, the human factors problems of humans interacting with highly automated systems across various fields. The paper then presents the HADRIAN approach for HSI for this field focusing on (1) human mobility needs as starting and converging point for engineering and research efforts, (2) strengthening holistic system definitions, (3) iterative design combined with risk and opportunity management, and (4) the application of naturalistic research methods including human-in-the-loop simulation.

Keywords: Human-Systems Integration, automated driving, driver role definition

1 Introduction

Highly automated driving promises to offer improved safety together with a multitude of previously unimagined possibilities such as novel mobility offerings for otherwise excluded mobility participants, reduced stress, and more meaningful activities while driving. Fully autonomous driving consists of vehicles operating without human interaction under virtually all operating conditions (SAE Level 5, see [1]). However, widespread implementation of fully autonomous operations currently appears still highly unlikely over the next ten years or so. Therefore, the human will likely remain to be involved as driver to interact with driving automation systems. For example,

during conditional automated driving (SAE Level 3, see [1]) the vehicle may drive without human supervision for some time but may then request to give back control to the human.

This is a departure from traditional modes of interaction between humans and technology and causes a challenge for human-systems integration. Over centuries, control was clearly allocated to the human and many useful tools from hammers to washing machines were designed with the human firmly in control despite increasingly sophisticated functionality and increasing automation. However, as technologies such as self-driving vehicles become smarter, they may take over tasks that were previously firmly in the hands of the humans. The traditional line of what humans and what technology can do blurs and with this human-systems integration challenges appear. In safety-critical systems where control authority has to shift between humans and technology under real time constraints, the overall system has to be designed with very detailed knowledge about the human capabilities and the possible environmental interactions.

Such knowledge is traditionally brought by human factors engineers, ergonomists, and engineering psychologists into the engineering process. Whereas human factors engineering is mostly concerned with applying knowledge about the human to create safe, acceptable, and effective human-system interaction, engineering psychology develops knowledge and theories about the human interacting with technological systems and ergonomics contributes the physiological constraints and capabilities of the human body. All these disciplines are here referred to as human factors disciplines. Thereby, human factors disciplines are by default brought relatively late into the technological system development process; at the time these contributions enter the engineering cycle, usually the overall system has already been designed and functions have been allocated between humans and system.

While the late involvement of the human factors disciplines into the engineering domain may have disadvantages in conventional product design, it is exacerbated in the design of safety critical systems where control authority shifts have to occur in real time. Accordingly, there has been, over the years, an increasing call for the discipline of Human-Systems Integration or HSI to help design technical systems that are from the start up closer aligned with the human capabilities and limitations. Thereby, HSI is not just about designing the interactions between humans and systems but about contributing to designs of overall systems that are consistent with human capabilities and limitations.

The increased call for HSI has been initially most notable in the design of large systems such as airspace or military systems where human factors has been established for the longest time. Specifically, in 2007 several experts investigated human-systems integration among various domains and identified concrete recommendations for successful HSI [2]. Also, in 2015 the American Psychological Association published a handbook to describe the psychological perspectives on such system developments and the international council of system-engineering in its handbook defines the importance of human systems integration [3]. There HSI is defined as „...the interdisciplinary technical and management process used to ensure that the human elements of

a system are appropriately addressed and integrated within the wider systems engineering lifecycle and management approach to a project.”

Several principles for successful HSI are stated in [2], most importantly that HSI should be brought early into the project planning and management and continue throughout the development. Also, the importance of including risk- and opportunity-driven approaches as well as the need for including HSI into the overall balancing and orchestration of systems engineering and project management are stressed. In my personal experience, this is made more difficult in real life because HSI requirements are usually less tightly specifiable than technical requirements. Overcoming the tendency and not only including in technical developments what can be tightly defined as technical requirements requires larger managerial and organizational structures, such as proposed by HSI.

2 Human Systems Integration Challenges for Automated Driving

This paper focuses on two HSI challenges in automotive engineering that the HADRIAN project sets out to address. The first is the exploration of **non-holistic solution spaces** as result of developing for many decades manually driven automotive vehicles. The second challenge are **human factors challenges** of interacting with high levels of automation when negotiating control authority under real time. Both challenges are discussed next in turn.

2.1 Non-Holistic Solution Exploration

A considerable challenge for HSI in automated driving consists of a historic legacy of successfully building cars at increasingly quality over many decades. Over more than 100 years of automobile development have engrained the viewpoints that put the vehicle firmly into the center of the engineering focus and thereby preselects what the driver has to do with the car within the existing road environment. Sophisticated evolutionary refinement processes that have continuously improved vehicles and added novel features now face a discontinuity to develop self-driving vehicles. The complexity of engineering a self-driving vehicle is considerably beyond the complexity of developing a manually driven car as many new challenges appear. Suddenly, topics like object recognition, scene interpretation, conflict resolution, and active safety prediction become important. To solve all these problems on the vehicle itself may be possible but maybe there are larger, more holistic approaches feasible to allocate the necessary functions for automated driving differently?

From a point of view of “learn from the past to address the problems of the future”, automobile developments of course focus on the vehicle as the main entity; the vehicle, though connected, is expected to address challenges of automated driving. The large variability of driving contexts, traffic rules and road user habits, as well as visibility and road conditions will be resolved by the vehicle itself as this is the area that a vehicle manufacturer can control best. However, this view actually makes the human

operator a weak link because he has to resolve all the problems that the driving automation cannot resolve (i.e. up to level 3 automated driving where the system detects any need to delegate control back to the human, see [1]). This viewpoint is here referred to as *solipsistic* viewpoint according to the philosophy that the self is the center of what is known to exist. The *solipsistic* viewpoint also stands against any extension of this limited self-view: the drunk pedestrian searching his keys only within the light of the streetlamp is the prototypical solipsist.

Another and wider view of the solution space consists of combining the various key-elements of automated driving, the vehicle, the road and traffic infrastructure, and the human, and include them jointly into the solution. The ambition here is to consider the self-driving system as composed of all these components. Such larger system views are more inherent in other domains such as aviation and railroad transportation where common infrastructure and control providers are explicit part of the complete operation. Low visibility landings on airports are only possible because of the existence of signaling infrastructure on the airports. Railroads are not just networks of rails but highly sophisticated signaling and control-systems that coordinate the flow of trains across a complex rail network. This centralized perspective is almost absent in automotive road transport and the question is how much better could self-driving vehicles perform if they would be supported on their trip through geographically fixed sensors and control infrastructure? We do not yet know but this may result in a profound change in the reliability and pervasiveness of the automated driving operation which then clearly impacts the role of the human. The HADRIAN project investigates such alternative viewpoint as will be described in Section 3.1.

2.2 Human Factors of Automation

The second challenge for the human-systems integration consists of a well-known set of human factors issues that result from the real time interaction with automation (e.g. [4]–[8]):

- a) **Driver-out-of-the-loop:** As the active driving task is transferred to automation, the driver's attention and involvement in the driving task are reduced. This can create a challenge concerning the transition from automated to manual driving as the driver has to regain situational awareness and control over the vehicle after possibly long periods of disengagement.
- b) **Trust-calibration:** As the driver stays disengaged from the driving task, the drivers' trust in the automated driving functionality is of paramount importance as this decides on acceptance and usage of automated driving features. A commonly observed phenomenon in trust research is that initial over-trust in the system (the system behaves as expected) is incorrectly extrapolated into expectations for situations in which the system actually does not work appropriately. For example, drivers of the automated driving (AD) level 2 lane-keeping functionality often experience that their otherwise well-functioning lane-keep assist (LKA) does not work correctly in traffic circles and unexpected LKA disconnects may occur. Such experiences, without explanation or understanding for its causes, may lead the driver to experience under-trust, generalized expectations about the lack of trustworthiness. Only with time and experience, drivers learn to

calibrate their trust to the appropriate levels as they get to know the intricacies of their AD vehicle. Without such trust calibration, the acceptance and use of the automated driving functionality may fail over time.

- c) **Humans are good controllers but bad monitors:** Humans are better at performing active control tasks that keep them actively in the loop rather than pure monitoring and supervising tasks. Active control tasks are also often perceived as rewarding, such that driving in certain environments is a highly pleasurable and sought-after activity. However, low-level repetitive monitoring tasks are difficult for humans as their attention is easily diverted to other tasks and therefore has to be actively maintained. A result can be reduced level of cognitive engagement [9].
- d) **Understanding of intent:** The mutual understanding of the actors' intent is a common prerequisite for safe traffic operations. Intent plays a role not only in the road environment such as when merging in traffic streams or negotiating priorities in road intersections. Understanding the other actor's intent is also important when a human need to take over control from the automation during AD level transitions. Like two dance-partners, automation and the human have to know and anticipate the behaviour of the other actor so that the overall vehicle behaviour can be safe before, during, and after an AD level transition. Because of the apparent differences between the involved actors, the understanding and negotiation of intent between humans and automated driving vehicles is of paramount importance for successful integration of automated driving in mixed traffic environments and cities. Also, the natural negotiations of intent are evolving as intelligently acting traffic participants immediately start seeking to take advantage of simple rule-based traffic-behaviour such that correctly and consistently behaving AD vehicles could become the losing players in the dynamic game of traffic negotiations (such as a human traffic participant pretending to step onto the road just to force an AD vehicle to stop or human drivers slipping into the larger, safe gaps that adaptive cruise control leave behind lead vehicles). Human factors research has started recently to investigate the many cues that human drivers use in negotiating their intent [5]–[10]. While scientific understanding about intent coordination between traffic actors is growing, it is our challenge to implement this knowledge in smart systems that correctly infer intent from humans and share their intent so that humans can easily understand them.
- e) **Mode Awareness:** Mode awareness is a common phenomenon of humans interacting with automation and is specifically well documented in the aviation domain where increasingly complex automation makes it difficult for the human to understand in what mode the automation is [16]. In automated driving, a commonly reported case of mode awareness is the difficulty of drivers to differentiate between different AD levels, especially 2, 3 and 4: in normal operations, these AD levels can be difficult to distinguish by the vehicle behaviour.

3 An Approach for HSI in Automated Driving

Novel ways of HSI for operations of higher automated driving vehicles are investigated by the HADRIAN project. HADRIAN is funded by the EU H2020 program and stands for “Holistic Approach for Driver Role Integration and Automation Allocation for European Mobility Needs”. The consortium investigates and defines the driver role for automated vehicles. The consortium partners are Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH, University of Granada, Northern Technical University of Athens, VDI/VDE-IT, TecNALIA, RWTH Aachen, BAST, CEA, IESTA, Nervtech, TU Delft, ASFINAG, AVL, FORD, University of Surrey, Paris-Lodron Universität Salzburg. The HADRIAN project specifically addresses the challenges of creating safe, acceptable, and effective solutions by applying several principles of HSI that. The main elements of the HADRIAN project as they relate to addressing the HSI challenges are the following components:

3.1 Human Needs as Starting Point

Human and societal mobility needs are the starting points for the HADRIAN approach to define the mission that the automated driving technologies should achieve. Putting human mobility needs as a starting point is hoped to provide the kind of multi-domain convergence across different partners because they allow to derive commonly understandable and hopefully acceptable objectives for the design and development activities.

Considering human needs as starting point for technological developments is not new (e.g. [17]) but *needs* are often insufficiently explained or understood. The term “human need” is here not directly considered a scientifically defined concept but one that is used pragmatically. For example, Maslow’s theory of the hierarchy of needs [18] continues to be frequently cited even today but has not received much scientific confirmation, see e.g. [19]. Instead of defining human needs as derivation of a generally valid theory of human motivation, we define needs in the sense of examples that an informed, and at least somewhat compassionate observer could identify when confronted with the specific situation of one or more individuals.

Knowledge about human behavior, values, beliefs, and constraints are necessary starting points but not sufficient for the identification of human needs. For example, knowledge about the situation of elderly drivers is abundant (e.g. [20]–[24]). Elderly drivers may have driven their whole life, may have lost their partners, and now are expected to continue to live alone at home to avoid retirement homes. Now they are faced with a situation where due to some deterioration of cognitive, perceptual, and motor capabilities they get excluded from driving their own car and lose their freedom to shop, visit, and run errands by themselves, especially when living in non-urban areas. By reviewing these constraints, there is nothing forcing someone to identify a need directly, except by some empathic understanding and interpretation of the factors influencing a meaningful life.

Another example consists of the interests and capabilities of today’s truck drivers who are increasingly confronted with complex technologies that require monitoring,

supervising and control. This has a direct impact on their work satisfaction can impact how professional drivers perceive their work and stay engaged and motivated over extended hours to drive safely and efficiently.

In this sense, empirical knowledge about human capabilities and conditions is a necessary contributor but is not itself sufficient to serve as needs in the design and development process. It requires a compassionate observer to pick up these needs as opportunities for technological development und appropriate HSI.

Therefore, the term human needs as it is described here is not directly a result of empirical research but based on an active joining of knowledge factors from four different viewpoints, see Figure 1.

Figure 1 Human Needs at the Junction of four Influencing Factors

3.2 Holistic versus Solipsistic System Definition

Once the needs have been identified and can be formulated as the mission for a technological development, the HADRIAN solution finding process will proceed in a holistic way to not exclude solutions too early. Holistic means that a “large enough” view is taken concerning the methods that could be used to achieve the solution. In the context of automated driving, usually the vehicle is in the center of the solution finding process. However, environmental constraints and road and traffic infrastructure as well as the human driver or operator should be taken in consideration and included as potential part of the solution.

Context diagrams are used in systems engineering to depict the limits of a system by defining what is outside and inside (see e.g. [25]). A solipsistic approach thereby reduces the system to the minimal components, usually the components that the developer has most control over. For a vehicle manufacturer this could be the vehicle itself. The interaction with other elements is of course acknowledged but are considered external entities that are outside the (current) levels of control. A holistic approach defines the system by initially including other entities that may be currently outside of the control of the system but could be highly relevant to provide a good systems solution. Doing so brings other stakeholders inside the system definition process instead of dealing with them as outsiders.

Implementing holistic, more inclusive views of systems allows for shifts in collaboration processes and structures toward common mission and objectives. This is not possible in solipsistic system definitions where the established communication channels are just reinforced. Holistic approaches take more time and include diverse activities that lead toward forming a more comprehensive coordination infrastructure among the stakeholders who are now becoming parts of the system instead of being outside of it. The main difference between solipsistic and holistic approaches is that the holistic approach may create convergence of the different stakeholders toward common objectives whereas solipsistic processes have to rely on others to do that.

Figure 2 Holistic versus Solipsistic Approach to Engineering a DAS

3.3 Iterative Design and Risk and Opportunity Management

HADRIAN is based on an important prerequisite of successful HSI such that the human constraints and limitations often only become visible when humans interact with a system for the first time under realistic constraints and conditions. Transitioning from automated to manual driving or flying can go well most of the time but statistically the likelihood of the errors only becomes visible when transitions are executed many times under myriads of circumstances and by different humans.

This problem is difficult to come by but the best existing solution to this problem seems to iteratively develop solutions and expose humans to them under approximated real conditions. The human is brought early on into the process and his interactions with the vehicle are observed such as in paper-and-pencil tests or human-in-the-loop simulations. Early iterations thereby already inform overall system risks that can then be used to manage the overall research and development process. Such a risk driven approach is also one of the recommended management practices of [2] and should probably be considered as inherent to the engineering of complex systems where unforeseen and unforeseeable uncertainties can dominate the development process. Similarly, opportunities should be taken into account and managed along with risks.

3.4 Naturalistic Research Methods

To integrate humans and systems requires knowledge about the system, the humans as well as the environment within which interactions occur. Specialty fields like psychology and human factors often focus on the generation of context-independent truths. Thereby, it can be difficult to apply the theories and principles of human behavior to the realistic usage conditions within the context of the real world. For example, much research in cognitive psychology has investigated human memory using non-sense syllables to extract principles about human memory by eliminating unwanted interference of word meanings and associations. While useful and important on a theoretical level, it is not straightforward to translate these findings into realistic environments such as designing a system that causes fewer human memory errors.

Therefore, to execute successful HSI, knowledge about the human is required to consider the naturalistic conditions of where the humans meet the system and interact with it. The boundary conditions of the situation need to be considered: for example, the attention of drivers in real life vary considerably from those in the laboratory environment and this must be taken into account when designing and testing cockpit displays. Also, testing older drivers to ensure they are still fit to drive puts the driver into a difficult situation because of stress under test conditions that can lead to an underestimation of the driving skills and inducing potentially dramatic life changes for elders. Understanding the presence and impact of such boundary conditions should therefore frame the application of psychological and ergonomic principles and theories.

The idea of naturalistic research considerations is not new as such approaches have become well-established in systemic safety assessments (e.g. [26]). There, the understanding of the larger situation and preconditions for accidents has become critical for the pervasive efforts to increase system safety. For example, the crash of Asiana Flight 214 ([27]) where pilots failed to monitor their airspeed upon approach to San Francisco airport has many causal preconditions. Some of these preconditions seem endemic to the use of highly automated systems and the difficulties of mode awareness even of highly experienced, professional pilots. Such problems are difficult to derive from psychological theories per se though the phenomena can certainly be explained by them.

To address these problems, research approaches such as “macro-cognition” have been proposed and are being applied around the world [28]. In contrast to micro-cognitive approaches where human performance is investigated under highly controlled and often artificial conditions to ensure controllability rather than external validity, macro-cognition emphasizes the environmental and larger task conditions within which the individual interacts with a system. Such macro-cognitive approaches seem necessary for successful HSI. Especially, methods such as real-world observations, expert interviews, and human-in-the-loop simulations are useful for this purpose.

Conclusions

The outlined challenges and principles of HSI are currently investigated in the EU H2020 HADRIAN project that started in Dec 2019 that will run until May 2023. If you are interested in updates and outcomes of the project you are encouraged to contact the author and visit the project website at <https://hadrianproject.eu/>.

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